

THICKNESS CONSTRAINTS IN COMPOSITE JOINTS

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SUMMARY: Mechanical fasteners are commonly used for composite joining. However, only two-dimensional configurations are commonly investigated in the study of composite joining. This study investigates the effects of three-dimensional scaling on the strengths of composite joints. Double-lap-single-pin joints made of glass/epoxy composite laminates were used in the investigations. Experimental results revealed that the joint strengths decreased as the joint sizes increased. However, as the joint size increased, the damage mode of composite joints also changed from initial bearing damage followed by final net-section failure for small joint sizes to direct catastrophic net-section failure for large joint sizes. It was found from experiments that the constraints in the thickness direction played a key role in the damage processes. Three factors were identified to be responsible for the constraints in the thickness direction. They were composite thickness, bonding strength through the laminate thickness and clamping force from bolting. Composite joints with low thickness constraints tended to have fiber buckling and delamination which resulted in initial bearing damage before final net-section failure. Since they showed larger displacement to failure and higher energy absorption during damage processes, composite joints having initial bearing damage followed by final net-section failure were more ductile than those experienced direct catastrophic net-section failure.

KEYWORDS: glass/epoxy composites, mechanical joints, thickness constraints, size effects, damage modes

1. INTRODUCTION

Joining is a secondary process in structure manufacturing. In manufacturing conventional metallic structures, small components are fabricated individually and then assembled to form large sections. Although complex polymer composite structures can be molded in single pieces to simplify manufacturing processes and to reduce assembly cost, they cannot be completely exempted from joining process. The joining process is especially needed when polymer composite components are to be assembled with components made of dissimilar materials such as metals.

Both mechanical fastening and adhesive bonding are commonly used in structure assembling. As structure components to be assembled become thicker, both the diameter and length of mechanical fasteners should be increased proportionally. Similarly, the bonding areas in the plane and through the thickness [1] of the structure components should be increased in adhesive bonding. The increase in the diameter and length of mechanical fasteners and the increase in the bonding areas of adhesive bonding, however, are not purely geometrical scaling issues. Material properties should also be considered as the sizes increase.

The studies of scaling for composite structures can be divided into in-plane scaling, thickness scaling and three-dimensional scaling. In studying in-plane scaling, thin composite laminates without notches [2] and with notches [3] were investigated. The strengths of composite laminates were found to decrease monotonically with the increase of in-plane dimensions. In a two-dimensional study on mechanical

fastening, Wang et al [4] reported that the bearing strength had a first-decrease-then-increase change as the in-plane dimensions increased.

Thickness also plays an important role in composite size scaling [5-8]. In fact, there is a special concern in scaling the thickness of composite laminates. Being different from simply increasing or decreasing the thickness in scaling the thickness of conventional metals, there exists at least two different ways in scaling the thickness of composite laminates, so-called sub-laminate scaling and ply-thickness scaling. The thickness scaling is actually more complicated than in-plane dimension scaling since both material properties and geometrical parameters are involved in the thickness scaling. More specifically, the non-uniform material properties induced by thickness scaling and the non-uniform stresses through laminate thickness caused by fastener bending due to large thickness [9-11] render the study very complicated. In a previous study [12], the thickness effect in composite pin joints was found to be dependent on the ratio of laminate thickness H to hole diameter D , i.e. H/D . Joint configurations with ratios of H/D around one were found to have more adequate performance than those with ratios of H/D greater than one.

Combining the in-plane dimension scaling and the thickness scaling, the three-dimensional size scaling needs to be understood before designers could predict the performance of large composite assemblies based on properties of small models, especially when thick composite laminates are of primary concern. The objective of this study is to investigate the effects of three-dimensional size scaling on the performance of composite mechanical fasteners.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Composite laminates made from glass/epoxy prepreg tapes were investigated in the study. Cross-ply laminates were of interest. They were made with alternate 0° and 90° plies and their stacking sequences can be expressed by $[0/90/0/90\dots]_n$ where n is the total number of plies. Three composite laminates having 9 plies ($n=9$), 17 plies ($n=17$) and 34 plies ($n=34$) were prepared. Their thicknesses were 3.30mm, 6.48mm and 12.95mm, respectively.

Double-lap-single-pin joints were used as the experimental model. The glass/epoxy composite laminates were used as central laps of joints while steel plates were used as outer laps, resulting in steel-composite dissimilar-material joints. The steel outer plates had thicknesses half those of composite central laps, warranting that the damage of joints was dominated by the damage of composite central laps. For mechanical fastening, steel pins designated as M-2 according to AISI classification system were used. The hardness of the steel pins was in the range of 63-65 based on the Rockwell C Hardness standards.

In designing composite joints, the geometrical elements include the joint width W , the hole diameter D , the laminate thickness H , the distance between the hole center and the joint end E , and the distance between the hole center and the gripping end L , also called the joint length. The associated geometrical ratios W/D , E/D , H/D and L/W are also important parameters in studying mechanical fastening. In order to have bearing damage, at least initially, instead of net-section damage or shear-out damage, W and E were chosen to be four times the hole diameter, resulting in $W/D=4$ and $E/D=4$. For identification purposes, each composite joint was assigned with a notation of $HXDY$, where H and D were laminate thickness and hole diameter, respectively, while X and Y were the ply number of the composite laminate and the hole diameter in millimeter (mm), respectively.

Three composite joints were prepared based on three-dimensional scaling. Since the composite laminates used in the study had a thickness scaling ratio of 1:1.97:3.92, i.e. 3.30mm:6.48mm:12.95mm, the closest integer ratio of 1:2:4 was used for scaling all other dimensions D , W and E . Since H/D was an important parameter in the thickness study and $H/D=1$ was found to be the critical value for composite joints to have load-displacement relations with distinct maximum loads [13], the hole diameter was chosen to be as close to the laminate thickness as possible. Based on the availability of drill bits and M2 pins, hole

diameters of 3.18mm (1/8"), 6.35mm (1/4") and 12.7mm (0.5") were used in the study, resulting in H9D3.18, H17D6.35 and H34D12.7 joints.

3. JOINT PROPERTIES

A. LOAD-DISPLACEMENT RELATIONS: Load-displacement relations bore important information concerning properties of joints. Beyond the initial linear ranges, all load-displacement curves seemed to exhibit two different types of profiles that could be categorized as ductile type and brittle type. Figure 1 gives an example for each type. The ductile-type curve shown in Figure 1(a) was obtained from an H9D3.18 joint. It featured a small but noticeable loss in load right after a local maximum load. This loss in load was found to be associated with bearing damage. The value of load usually recovered itself as loading process continued before another load loss occurred. This second load loss, however, was drastic and non-recoverable and was found to be associated with the net-section damage. The brittle-type curve shown in Figure 1(b) was based on an H34D12.7 joint. It showed a continuously smooth relation until a catastrophic drop of load, which was found to be associated with net-section damage, occurred.

B. MAXIMUM LOADS AND JOINT STRENGTHS: Based on Figures. 1(a) and 1(b), the strengths of composite joints may be defined by the maximum loads. An "offset of displacement" associated with the maximum load was also presented for further evaluations. The "offset of displacement" was defined as the distance between the initial linear segment of a load-displacement curve and a line passing through the maximum load and parallel to the linear segment. A term named "percentage of offset of displacement" was further defined as the percentage of the ratio of the "offset of displacement" to the hole diameter. The presentation of the "percentage of offset of displacement" was aimed at the justification of maximum loads. The percentages of offsets of displacement of all joints ranged from 4% to 7%. The identifications of maximum loads for joints with different types of load-displacement relations, i.e. the ductile type and the brittle type, were thus justified. Once the maximum loads of joints were identified, they were divided by corresponding bearing-contact areas, i.e. DH, to determine the bearing strengths.

C. MACROSCOPIC AND MICROSCOPIC DAMAGE MODES: Because it was less catastrophic than net-section damage and shear-out damage, bearing damage was preferred if the failure of mechanical fasteners was to take place. Accordingly $W/D=4$ and $E/D=4$ were imposed to all joints in order to have bearing damage, at least initially. However, not all composite joints investigated in the present study started failure with initial bearing damage. Composite joints of H9D3.18 and H17D6.35 had initial bearing damage prior to ultimate net-section failure. However, the dominant damage mode of H34D12.7 joints was the direct catastrophic net-section failure. In an effort to further understand the process of damage, microscopic damage modes in the neighborhood of bearing-contact zones were also examined.

Figure 2 shows the microscopic damage of an H17D6.35 joint. As shown in Figure 2(a), there are matrix cracks along the net-section lines and delamination underneath the bearing-contact zone. On the cross-section along the laminate centerline, zig-zag kinks can be found in the 0° plies as shown in Figure 2(b). The fiber kinks were the results of fiber buckling due to the high compressive stress around the contact-bearing zone. The microscopic damage of H9D3.18 was similar to that of H17D6.35. However, the microscopic damage around the bearing zones of H34D12.7 joints was relatively insignificant; only very few fiber kinks were found in the 0° -plies close to the laminate surfaces. It seemed a correlation between macroscopic damage and microscopic damage could be established.

4. ASSEMBLED AND LAMINATED COMPOSITES

A. ASSEMBLING TECHNIQUES: Thick composite laminates have many applications in heavy-duty structures such as armored vehicles. However, their costs are high and their properties are not uniform due to uneven curing cycles, especially in the thickness direction [14,15]. Assembling thin composite laminates together to form thick composite structures was found to be feasible in reducing cost and achieving property uniformity. Techniques such as adhesive bonding, riveting and clamping were

presented in previous studies on assembled composites [16,17]. It was found that the impact resistance of assembled composites was very comparable with that of laminated counterparts. The present study investigated mechanical fasteners in both assembled and laminated composites. The comparisons of joining strengths and damage processes were of primary interests.

In studying assembled composites, two 9-ply laminates were bonded together with a room-curing epoxy to form an assembled composite. Because the total thickness of the assembled composite was close to that of H17D6.35 laminated composite, for comparison purpose, a resembling 6.35mm-diameter hole was prepared in the assembled composite for mechanical fastening. For identification purpose, the assembled composite was designated as H9x2D6.35-B where B stands for bonded. If the two 9-ply laminates were simply put together and contacted each other without any form of bonding, a notation of H9x2D6.35-C (C for contacted) was used for the assembled composite. The geometric elements and ratios of the mechanical fasteners made of the assembled composites were similar to those of the laminated counterpart, i.e. H17D6.35, so were the experimental parameters.

In a similar investigation, four 9-ply laminates were bonded together to form an assembled composite. Since it had a total thickness close to that of the 34-ply laminates, i.e. H34D12.7, a hole of 12.7mm in diameter was prepared in the assembled composite for mechanical fastening. A notation of H9x4D12.7-B was used to identify the assembled composite. Similarly, a notation of H17x2D12.7-B was used for an assembled composite bonding two 17-ply laminates together.

B. NORMALIZED STRENGTHS: Table 1 gives experimental results of the joints. Besides the averaged strengths, normalized strengths are also presented in the table. The normalized strengths were obtained from dividing averaged joint strengths by corresponding numbers of layers that had fibers oriented in the loading directions. The normalized strengths were presented due to the fact that the laminated composites and the assembled counterparts did not have the same numbers of total layers, nor did they had the same numbers of layers with fibers oriented in the loading directions, i.e. 0° -direction in the present study. For example, the laminated composite H34D12.7 had a total number of 34 plies; and only 17 out of the 34 plies were in the 0° -direction. The assembled counterpart H9x4D12.7-B had a total number of 36 plies; and only 20 out of the 36 plies were in the 0° -direction.

Experimental results of the joints based on assembled composites and laminated counterparts are given in Table 1. The normalized strengths of the two assembled composites H9x4D12.7-B and H17x2D12.7-B were 10% lower than that of the laminated counterpart, i.e. H34D12.7. However, the normalized strengths of the bonded composite H9x2D6.35-B and unbonded composite H9x2D6.35-C were about the same as that of the laminated counterpart, i.e. H17D6.35. It seemed the assembled composites could resemble the laminated composites up to some extent, at least, as far as mechanical fastening was concerned.

C. ULTIMATE FAILURE: Besides the joint strength, another important experimental result was associated with the damage process. All specimens investigated in the study seemed to fail with initial bearing damage except H34D12.7, which experienced direct catastrophic net-section damage. The interpretation of this phenomenon is stated as follows. Being compared with H9x2D6.35-B, H9x2D6.35-C and H17D6.35, H34D12.7 was more constrained in the thickness direction due to its larger thickness. Being compared with H9x4D12.7 and H17x2D12.7, H34D12.7 was more constrained in the thickness direction due to its better bonding through the laminate thickness. Accordingly, the constraint in the thickness direction played a key role in the damage process. A composite with more constraint in the thickness direction had higher resistance to fiber buckling and delamination, resulting in direct catastrophic net-section damage. In contrast, a composite with less constraint in the thickness direction was more prone to fiber

buckling and delamination. For example, the H17D6.35 joint shown in Figure 2(a) resulted in initial bearing damage prior to final net-section damage.

Although their geometrical elements and ratios were about the same, H9x4D12.7, H17x2D12.7 and H34D12.7 joints had different damage processes. The former two types had initial bearing damage prior to final net-section damage while the latter one had direct catastrophic net-section damage. Initial bearing damage was an important damage mode in composite fasteners [13], at least in thin composites. The primary mechanism of the bearing damage was fiber buckling and delamination. They rendered composite joints more ductile. Although H34D12.7 had the highest normalized strength, it had the lowest displacement to failure. The total energy absorbed by H34D12.7 due to damage formation, which was equal to the area under the load-displacement curve, was also smaller than those absorbed by the assembled counterparts, i.e. H9x4D12.7 and H17x2D12.7. In fact, it was easier to have delamination on the assembled interfaces than on the laminated interface because the adhesive bonding strength on the assembly interfaces was lower than the matrix bonding strength on the laminated interfaces. Once delaminated, the disassembled thin laminates were prone to fiber buckling and delamination, i.e. the bearing damage. In contrast, the laminated counterpart H34D12.7 was not vulnerable to delamination, except those interfaces very close to the laminate surfaces. As a result, the bearing damage was insignificant in H34D12.7 joints. They failed by direct catastrophic net-section damage.

5. DIFFERENCE BETWEEN PINNED AND BOLTED JOINTS

A. CONSTRAINTS IN THICKNESS DIRECTION: The constraint in the thickness direction played a key role in the damage process of composite fasteners. The higher the constraint in the thickness direction, the higher the resistance of composite to fiber buckling and delamination. Hence, a composite joint with high constraint in the thickness direction, such as H34D12.7, would result in direct catastrophic net-section damage, i.e. a relatively brittle-type failure. However, a composite joint with low constraint in the thickness direction, such as H9x4D12.7, would result in initial bearing damage prior to final failure, i.e. a relatively ductile-type failure. Another way to verify the shift of failure mode from a ductile type to a brittle type as the constraint in the thickness direction increased was to compare pinned joints with bolted counterparts since the latter had additional constraints, i.e. clamping forces, in the thickness directions.

B. BOLTED JOINTS: Although pinned joints were commonly used in research studies, bolted joints were more practical in structure assembly. In fact, the clamping force used in bolted joints seemed to enhance the joining strength [18,19]. Godwin et al [20] had shown that a pinned joint had the lowest strength, a fully bolted joint had the highest strength, while a riveted joint had a strength between the two extremes.

In comparing the pinned and the bolted joints, H17D6.35, H9x2D6.35-B and H9x2D6.35-C joints were used. The clamping force for the bolted joints was 20 Nm. The experimental results were given in Table 1. The normalized strengths of the bolted joints were slightly higher than those of the pinned counterparts. This result was consistent with that obtained from the comparisons among H9x4D12.7, H17x2D12.7 and H34D12.7 cases.

There was also a shift in damage mode due to the increase of constraint in the thickness direction. For pinned joints, i.e. H9x2D6.35-B and H9x2D6.35-C, the damage modes showed initial bearing damage prior to final net-section damage; for bolted counterparts, however, direct catastrophic net-section damage dominated. Since the only variation introduced was the clamping force in the thickness direction, this result further verified the important role of the through-the-thickness constraint in the behavior of joints. Apparently, the high constraint due to clamping force rendered the composite joints higher resistance to

delamination. Accordingly, direct catastrophic net-section damage, instead of initial bearing damage followed by final net-section damage, took place in the bolted joints.

In summary, the constraint in the thickness direction played a key role in both joining strength and damage process. A composite with a higher constraint based on larger thickness, better bonding through the thickness or clamping force in the thickness direction could increase the joining strength slightly. However, the higher constraint in the thickness direction rendered the composite more brittle, i.e. smaller displacement to failure and smaller energy absorption during failure process, and resulted in direct catastrophic net-section damage, instead of initial bearing damage followed by final net-section damage.

6. CONCLUSIONS

1. The load-displacement curves of the mechanical fasteners investigated in the study can be categorized as ductile type and brittle type. Both H9D3.18 and H17D6.35 joints had ductile-type load-displacement curves while H34D12.7 joints had brittle-type curves. The “percentage of offset of displacement” was presented to determine the maximum loads and the subsequent joint strengths.
2. There was a monotonic decrease in joint strength as the three-dimensional size increased. Although the final failure of all joints was due to net-section damage, the joints with the ductile-type load-displacement curves experienced initial bearing damage prior to final net-section damage while the joints with the brittle-type load-displacement curves failed by direct catastrophic net-section damage.
3. The constraint in the thickness direction played a key role in the damage process of composite fasteners. In addition to large thickness, good bonding through the thickness and adequate clamping force from bolting also contributed to the constraint in the thickness direction.
4. High constraint in thickness direction prevented fibers from bucking and composites from delamination. Composite joints with high constraints in the thickness direction failed in direct catastrophic net-section damage while those with low constraint in the thickness direction failed with initial bearing damage prior to final net-section damage.
5. Composite joints that failed with initial bearing damage had higher displacement to failure and higher energy absorption during failure process than those that failed with direct catastrophic net-section damage.

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Figure 1(a) – Load-displacement curve: brittle type (H9D3.18).

Figure 1(b) - Load-displacement curve: ductile type (H34D12.7).

Figure 2(a) - Front view of damage in an H17D6.35 joint.

Figure 2(b) - Cross-sectional view of damage in an H17D6.35 joint.

Table 1 – Comparison of strengths of composite joints.

	Type ¹	Max. Load (kN)	offset ² (%)	Mode ³	Type ¹	Max. Load (kN)	offset ² (%)	Mode ³	Type ¹	Max. Load (kN)	offset ² (%)	Mode ³
Pinned	H9x4D12.7-B				H17x2D12.7-B				H34D12.7			
	B	73.99	4.2	BR	B	67.19	5.7	BR	B	70.07	4.8	NS
	B	76.32	3.8	BR	B	64.91	5.2	BR	B	71.80	5.6	NS
	B	73.53	5.8	BR	B	69.67	7.0	BR	B	71.90	5.3	NS
Avg. Max. Load (kN)	74.61				67.25				71.25			
Avg. Strength (MPa) ⁴	421.31				410.09				431.85			
Norm. Strength (MPa) ⁵	21.06				22.79				25.48			
Pinned	H9x2D6.35-C				H9x2D6.35-B				H17D6.35			
	B	19.20	2.7	BR	B	20.38	5.1	BR	B	17.66	5.3	BR
	B	19.32	3.6	BR	B	19.90	6.6	BR	B	18.19	3.8	BR
	B	18.76	4.1	BR	B	19.55	4.3	BR	B	16.91	4.4	BR
					B	19.82	5.4	BR	B	17.15	5.0	BR
									B	19.19	6.0	BR
Avg. Max. Load (kN)	19.10				19.91				17.82			
Avg. Strength (MPa) ⁴	435.16				453.80				433.14			
Norm. Strength (MPa) ⁵	43.52				45.38				48.13			
Bolted	H9x2D6.35-C				H9x2D6.35-B				H17D6.35			
	B	20.65	7.4	NS	B	21.23	5.4	NS	B	19.87	5.8	NS
	B	20.46	7.0	NS	B	21.45	7.4	NS	B	19.35	3.8	NS
	B	20.44	6.9	NS	B	21.35	7.1	NS	B	20.31	4.2	NS
Avg. Max. Load (kN)	20.52				21.34				19.84			
Avg. Strength (MPa) ⁴	467.56				486.44				482.34			
Norm. Strength (MPa) ⁵	46.76				48.64				53.59			

¹ type of load-deformation curve: B for brittle and D for ductile

² percentage of offset of displacement at maximum load

³ Failure mode at maximum load: BR for bearing and NS for net-section

⁴ average maximum load per contact area (DH

⁵ average strength normalized by the number of 0° plies